

Association Between Screen Time and Anxiety Levels Among First-Year Medical Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT:

Background: During the COVID-19 pandemic, online learning and social restrictions increased students' dependence on electronic devices, resulting in higher screen time. Excessive screen time has been associated with mental health problems, including anxiety.

Objective: This study aimed to determine the relationship between screen time and anxiety levels among first-year medical students during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted among first-year students at the Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University, from September to November 2021. Data were collected using a screen time recall questionnaire and the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (ZSAS). Statistical analysis was performed using Fisher's exact test with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results: A total of 117 students participated in this study. Most participants had high computer/laptop screen time (90.6%) and high total screen time (71.8%). Anxiety assessment showed that 94.0% of participants had normal anxiety levels, while 6.0% experienced mild-to-moderate anxiety. Smartphone/tablet screen time was significantly associated with anxiety levels ($p=0.005$; $r=0.251$). However, television screen time, computer/laptop screen time, and total screen time were not significantly associated with anxiety ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: Smartphone/tablet screen time was significantly associated with anxiety levels among first-year medical students during the COVID-19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS: screen time, anxiety, medical students, COVID-19 pandemic, smartphone use, mental health

I. INTRODUCTION

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Indonesian government implemented health protocols and large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) to reduce the transmission of COVID-19. These measures included wearing masks, handwashing, physical distancing, limiting crowds, and reducing outdoor activities.¹

To minimize the spread of infection, educational institutions also implemented online learning. However, this learning method resulted in changes in students' daily routines and lifestyles that may negatively affect mental health. Several studies have reported increased anxiety levels among university students during the pandemic. A study conducted in Bangladesh found that university students experienced mild anxiety and decreased mental health status.² Similarly, a study among nursing students in Israel reported that 42.8% experienced moderate anxiety and 13.1% experienced severe anxiety.³ In Indonesia, data from the 2018 Basic Health Research showed that 9.8% of individuals aged ≥ 15 years experienced emotional mental disorders such as anxiety and depression.⁴

Anxiety is characterized by feelings of fear and worry accompanied by autonomic nervous system activation. Among students, anxiety may arise from several factors, including fear of infection, concerns about family health, difficulty concentrating, sleep disturbances, reduced social interaction due to physical distancing, and worries regarding academic performance.⁵ Persistent anxiety may also lead to somatic symptoms such as irritability, insomnia, and restlessness. First-year medical students may be particularly vulnerable to anxiety because of academic adjustment and increased educational demands during remote learning.

Social restrictions and online learning also increased the use of electronic devices among students, resulting in higher screen time.⁶ Increased screen time has been associated with various mental health problems, including anxiety. A study conducted in

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China demonstrated that high screen time was significantly associated with higher anxiety levels.⁷ Therefore, this study aimed to determine the relationship between screen time during the COVID-19 pandemic and anxiety levels among first-year students at the Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University.

II. METHOD

A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted from September to November 2021 at the Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University. Subjects were recruited using a consecutive sampling method based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were active first-year medical students aged 17–20 years who provided informed consent to participate in the study. Students with a history of psychiatric disorders, current COVID-19 infection, or chronic medical illnesses were excluded from the study.

Data collection was conducted using questionnaires administered through Google Forms and distributed via social media platforms. A total of 121 students who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were identified, of whom 117 agreed to participate and completed the informed consent form, while 4 declined participations.

Screen time data were collected using a screen time recall questionnaire that assessed daily activities related to the use of electronic media, including television, computers/laptops, and smartphones/tablets. The duration of each activity was recorded in minutes per day and summed to obtain the total daily screen time. Anxiety levels were assessed using the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (ZSAS).⁸

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. Bivariate analysis was performed using Fisher's exact test to assess the association between screen time and anxiety levels. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

This study was approved by the Health Research Ethics Commission (KEPK) of the Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University (No. 325/EC/KEPK/FK-UNDIP/VIII/2021).

III. RESULTS

A total of 117 first-year medical students participated in this study. Most participants were female (75.2%), and the majority were aged 19 years (66.7%). Based on screen time classification, most participants had high computer/laptop screen time (90.6%) and high total screen time (71.8%). High smartphone/tablet screen time was found in 48.7% of participants, whereas only 20.5% had high television screen time. Anxiety assessment using the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (ZSAS) demonstrated that most participants had normal anxiety levels (94.0%), while 6.0% experienced mild-to-moderate anxiety (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of the Study Participants

Variable	n	%
Sex		
Male	29	24.8
Female	88	75.2
Age (years)		
17	2	1.7
18	19	16.2
19	78	66.7
20	18	15.4
Television screen time		
High	24	20.5
Low	93	79.5
Computer/laptop screen time		
High	106	90.6
Low	11	9.4
Smartphone/tablet screen time		
High	57	48.7
Low	60	51.3
Total screen time		
High	84	71.8
Low	33	28.2
Anxiety		

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Mild-to-moderate	7	6.0
Normal	110	94.0

The association between screen time and anxiety levels is presented in Table 2. Fisher's exact test demonstrated a significant association between smartphone/tablet screen time and anxiety levels ($p=0.005$; $r=0.251$). Participants with high smartphone/tablet screen time showed a greater proportion of mild-to-moderate anxiety compared with participants with low smartphone/tablet screen time. No significant associations were found between anxiety levels and television screen time, computer/laptop screen time, or total screen time ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2. Association Between Screen Time and Anxiety Levels Among Participants

Variable	Anxiety n (%)		p-value	r
	Mild-to-Moderate	Normal		
TV screen time				
High	2 (8.3%)	22 (91.7%)	0.586	0.050
Low	5 (5.4%)	88 (94.6%)		
Computer/laptop screen time				
High	7 (6.6%)	99 (93.4%)	0.379	0.081
Low	0 (0%)	11 (100%)		
Smartphone/tablet screen time				
High	7 (12.3%)	50 (87.7%)	0.005*	0.251
Low	0 (0%)	60 (100%)		
Total screen time				
High	7 (8.3%)	77 (91.7%)	0.087	0.156
Low	0 (0%)	33 (100%)		

Fisher's Exact Test was used for statistical analysis; r = Phi coefficient.

* $p < 0.05$ indicates statistical significance.

IV. DISCUSSION

The present study found that most first-year medical students had high total screen time during the COVID-19 pandemic. Smartphone/tablet screen time was significantly associated with anxiety levels, whereas television screen time, computer/laptop screen time, and total screen time were not significantly associated with anxiety.

The high proportion of screen time observed in this study may be related to the implementation of online learning and social restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic, which increased students' dependence on electronic devices for academic and social activities. Similar findings were reported by Al-Khani et al., who found that medical students experienced increased screen time during the pandemic.⁹ In the present study, computer/laptop screen time was predominantly high among participants, likely because online lectures and academic assignments were conducted virtually. In contrast, television screen time was generally low, suggesting that students spent more time using smartphones and computers/laptops rather than watching television.

Most participants in this study had normal anxiety levels, while only a small proportion experienced mild-to-moderate anxiety. This finding is consistent with a large cross-sectional study conducted in China, which reported that only 7.7% of college students experienced anxiety disorders during the pandemic.¹⁰ However, previous studies conducted among medical students in Indonesia have reported varying anxiety prevalence, ranging from low to relatively high levels.^{11,12} These differences may be influenced by variations in academic environment, coping mechanisms, social support, and psychological resilience among students.

The present study demonstrated a significant association between smartphone/tablet screen time and anxiety levels. Students with higher smartphone/tablet screen time showed a greater proportion of mild-to-moderate anxiety compared with students with lower smartphone/tablet screen time. This finding is consistent with previous studies reporting that increased screen exposure was associated with higher anxiety symptoms during the COVID-19 pandemic.^{13,14} Several mechanisms may explain this relationship. Excessive smartphone use may increase exposure to social media, pandemic-related information, and academic stressors, which can contribute to psychological distress. In addition, prolonged screen exposure may disrupt sleep quality, reduce physical activity, and decrease direct social interaction, all of which may negatively affect mental health.

In contrast, television screen time, computer/laptop screen time, and total screen time were not significantly associated with anxiety levels in this study. One possible explanation is that computer/laptop use during the pandemic was primarily related to

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academic activities rather than entertainment or social media exposure. Similarly, television viewing may represent passive screen exposure with lower psychological engagement compared with smartphone use. This finding is supported by a previous study conducted by Khouja et al., which also found no significant association between screen time and anxiety.¹⁵

This study has several limitations. First, screen time data were obtained using self-reported questionnaires, which may have introduced recall bias. Second, the cross-sectional design of this study does not allow causal relationships between screen time and anxiety levels to be established. Third, this study was conducted only among first-year medical students at a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of the findings.

Despite these limitations, this study provides important information regarding the association between smartphone/tablet screen time and anxiety among medical students during the COVID-19 pandemic. Further studies with longitudinal designs and larger populations are needed to better understand the long-term effects of screen time on students' mental health.

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